

Leaf Anatomy of Herbal C₃, C₄, CAM, and Intermediate Plants from Arid and Semi-Arid Climate of Thar Desert

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Received : 14th January, 2024 ; Accepted : 15th February, 2024

DOI:- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13356754>

ABSTRACT

Thar Desert is a home of a diverse array of flora utilizing various photosynthetic pathways—C₃, C₄, and intermediate species. How do local fluctuations in seasonal events such as temperature and rainfall affect the functional leaf anatomy will be a future question of study. Under ambient climate we present here leaf anatomical evidence for such plants as a repository for arid plant adaptations. We observed leaf anatomy of herbaceous plants like C₄-Dicot *Mollugo cerviana*, *Gisekia pharnaceoides*, *Tribulus* sp., *Euphorbia* sp., *Heliotropium* sp., and C₄-Monocot such as *Cenchrus* sp., *Brachiaria* sp., *Lasiurus scindicus*, *Panicum* sp., *Chloris* sp., etc. for their exceptional strategies for coping with water scarcity during and after the brief rainy seasons. Their distinctive Kranz anatomy, well-developed bundle sheath cells, and unique chloroplast arrangements contribute to efficient CO₂ fixation, enabling them to thrive in arid climates. In contrast, C₃ plants such as *Corbichonia decumbens*, *H. curassavicum*, *Dipterygium glaucum* display distinctive leaf anatomies characterized by notable C₃ arrangements of palisade and spongy cells filled with chloroplasts. *M. nudicaulis*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Farsetia hamiltonii* show intermediate C₃-C₄ and *Portulaca grandiflora* show C₄ and CAM leaf anatomies. This is the first anatomical record of *Farsetia hamiltonii* as C₃-C₄ intermediate based on leaf anatomy. The pictorial cataloguing of these plants' anatomical traits will shed light on evolutionary adaptations and aid in understanding how these plants respond to changing climatic conditions in the Thar Desert.

Key Words - : Kranz Anatomy; C₃-C₄ Intermediate; Leaf anatomy; Bundle Sheath; Desert Plants

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INTRODUCTION

Most plants rely on the ancient C₃ photosynthetic pathway, where atmospheric CO₂ is directly fixed by the enzyme ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (Rubisco), initiating the Calvin–Benson–Bassham cycle (Alenazi *et al.*, 2023). Yet, Rubisco's ability to also bind O₂ initiates the energy-intensive photorespiratory pathway. To counter this, C₃ plants were gradually diversified into CAM and C₄ plants by elevating CO₂ concentration near Rubisco by following spatial (C₄

plants) and temporal (CAM) carbon concentration mechanism (CCM), enhancing photosynthetic efficiency. In C₄-CCM, the plants evolved to transport intermediate carbon compounds to bundle sheath cells whereas CAM-CCM plants fix the atmospheric carbon in night and stored in vacuole to avoid transpiration by keeping closed stomate in daytime (Mercado & Studer, 2022; Munekage & Taniguchi, 2022). This spatial isolation minimizes photorespiration Conversely, the

intermediate C₂ pathway recycles photo-respired CO₂ via glycine shuttling to bundle sheath cells, while the more sophisticated C₄ pathway, featuring Kranz anatomy, mitigates photorespiration by initiating CO₂ fixation using phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) carboxylase in mesophyll cells. This pathway produces a fourcarbon compound from PEP and CO₂, transferred to bundle sheath cells where all CO₂ fixation occurs in C₄ species (Mercado & Studer, 2022).

C₄ plants have a distinct leaf anatomy compared to C₃ plants, which significantly enhances their photosynthetic efficiency (Munekage & Taniguchi, 2022). A pivotal difference lies in the spatial separation of the CO₂ fixation and Calvin-Benson cycle processes within mesophyll and bundle sheath (BS) cells. In C₄ plants, BS cells take the lead in photosynthesis, while mesophyll cells focus solely on CO₂ fixation. This separation reduces carbon loss in mesophyll cells by notably reducing or eliminating RuBisCO expression there. Moreover, BS cells in C₄ plants are larger, house more chloroplasts, and maintain minimal to no RuBisCO, establishing a concentrated CO₂ environment that suppresses photorespiration. Their internal positioning within leaves further shields BS cells from atmospheric oxygen, sustaining the CO₂ to O₂ ratio and further curtailing photorespiration (Mercado & Studer, 2022; Munekage & Taniguchi, 2022). In earliest evidence, Haberlandt (Haberlandt 1882, 1914) identified the 'Kranz' arrangement of mesophylls in Cyperaceae and Gramineae families. The C₄ pathway's functionality requires metabolic cooperation between outer mesophyll (photosynthetic carbon assimilative) and inner bundle sheath (photosynthetic carbon reductive) tissues (Muhaidat *et al.*, 2007). Different patterns of mesophyll cell types in Chenopodiaceae have been identified, varying from non-Kranz-types to Kranz types (Jacobs 2001).

Examining how plants functionally adapt to changing environments often involves studying leaf anatomy. Leaves typically showcase arrangements of epidermal cells, mesophyll cells, bundle sheaths, and vascular bundles, which provide insights into

the plant's physiology regarding photosynthesis (Pathare *et al.*, 2020). Dicot leaves notably differ from monocot leaves in their arrangement of photosynthetic cells.

The study of leaf anatomy in plant populations within a specific area serves as a valuable tool for monitoring ecological shifts such as aridization, climate change, and the diminishing availability of water resources (Ivanova *et al.*, 2019). An increase in the prevalence of plant species exhibiting Kranz anatomy in their leaves is regarded as an indicator of heightened adaptation to dry, xerophilous habitats (Ivanova *et al.*, 2019; Heilmeyer, 2019)

Here we are presenting leaf anatomical pictorial evidence of all four C₃, C₄, CAM and intermediate types of plants growing under ambient climate of Thar arid regions.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Twenty-seven (27) plant species encompassing C₃, C₄, CAM and intermediate photosynthetic pathways were collected from the local arid and semi-arid regions of Jodhpur and Jaisalmer during 2016 to 2019 (Table 1). Species selection was based on availability within their natural habitat at the time of collection. At least three mature leaves were collected from each individual plant.

Leaf sectioning and Staining

The leaves were first washed with clean water and submerged in the water till use. Each leaf was cut for thin transverse sections by using a sharp razor such as blade. Hand-sections of the leaf with a uniform thickness of 0.02-0.03 mm were selected for staining. The sections were stained with either a 0.01% dilution of safranin (HiMedia©) or Toluene blue (HiMedia©).

Microscope Analysis

The stained sections were mounted in 50% Glycerin and observed under compound Microscope (Olympus) with 100X magnification. Images of leaf anatomy were captured using a digital camera (Canon) attached to the microscope.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The western Thar Desert represents one of India's hottest regions characterized by low rainfall,

intense temperatures, significant day-night temperature fluctuations with minimal humidity for more than half months of the year. Over the last 50 years, anthropogenic activities and global climate change have significantly impacted the desert's natural ecosystem, leading to the proliferation of weedy species during the rainy season. During peak floral diversity in the monsoonal season, these ephemeral plants complete their life cycle rapidly. The flora in this area faces various stresses, and these stresses are likely reflected in leaf functional anatomy. This highlights the resilience of desert flora, which has adapted to these challenging conditions through various mechanisms, including C_4 photosynthetic pathways (Tian *et al.*, 2016; Guo *et al.*, 2017).

Dominance of C_4 Anatomy and Variations

Our study found a predominance of C_4 leaf anatomy among the investigated plants, which align with evolutionary adaptation of desert plants to arid environments. These plants often employ carbon concentration mechanisms (CCM) for efficient photosynthesis and water use efficiency.

This finding aligns with established knowledge – C_4 plants dominant in grass species, with their characteristic Kranz anatomy (bundle sheath encircling vascular bundles), are particularly suited for xeric climates due to their enhanced water use efficiency and CO_2 fixation rates (Guo *et al.*, 2017). While grasses comprise roughly 60% of all C_4 plants, i.e. around 7500 species across various families (Sage, 2004). C_4 anatomy extends beyond this group. We also recorded C_4 anatomy in species of Cyperaceae, a family within the Poales order and in numerous eudicot families such as Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, Euphorbiaceae, and families within the extend of Caryophyllales order (Huang *et al.*, 2022). It is observed that these C_4 anatomies differ in the structure and arrangement of the dual layered chlorenchyma adjacent to vascular bundles. These variations involve features like water storage tissue, hypodermal cells, sclerenchyma, and continuous or interrupted Kranz tissue (Fig 1 and 2). Such anatomical disparities within C_4 plants reflect adaptations to diverse environmental

conditions and resource availability. For instance, grass species like *L. scindicus* and *P. turgidum* showcase enlarged bundle sheath cells, while perennial grasses often possess a higher count of bulliform cells (Fig 1 and 2). Apart from differences in mesophyll and bundle sheath tissues, three biochemical subtypes exist in C_4 photosynthesis based on the principal decarboxylation enzyme used in the Bundle Sheath: NADP-malic enzyme (NADP-ME), NAD-malic enzyme (NAD-ME), and Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase (PCK). PEPC, the initial enzyme common to all three subtypes, resides in mesophyll cells (Hatch, 1987; Kanai & Edwards, 1999). The distribution of these subtypes is significantly correlated with aridity and human domestication. NAD-ME species tend to dominate in arid C_4 vegetation, while NADP-ME species prevail in moister environments. Most of our domesticated majority of C_4 row crops, pasture plants, and weeds are NADP-ME type (Wang *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, dicot plants with C_4 anatomy typically exhibit centripetally arranged chloroplasts in bundle sheath cells (Fig 2), while C_4 grasses showcase differing chloroplast arrangements based on their biochemical subtype (Fig 1).

Additionally, leaf cross-sections contain mesophyll cells, primary sites of photosynthesis, comprising palisade (upper side) and spongy (lower side) cell types. C_4 -CAM intermediate *P. grandiflora* a small herbaceous annual plant, shows the C_4 photosynthetic pathway with characteristic of Pilooid-type Kranz leaf anatomy (Fig 2). *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *M. nudicaulis*, and *Farsetia hamiltonii* exhibited C_3 - C_4 intermediate anatomical features, indicating a transitional state between C_3 and C_4 pathways (Fig 2). Notably, *P. grandiflora* displayed C_4 -CAM intermediate anatomical characteristics. The key finding of the observations is identification of *Farsetia hamiltonii* as a new member of C_2 type plants (C_3 - C_4 intermediate) based on preliminary anatomical features. As per the literature survey, the plant is not recorded for its photosynthetic type. The leaf anatomy of *F. hamiltonii* shows the presence of bundle sheath around vascular bundles filled with

chloroplasts arranged in both centripetal and centrifugal patterns, alongside typical C₃ leaf anatomy characteristics such as differentiation of mesophyll cells into palisade and spongy cells (Fig 3). However, other evidence such as photosynthesis

rate for the CO₂ compensation point, C¹³ radio labelling for carbon trace in Bundle sheath, and TEM for chloroplast arrangement in bundle sheath will be further required confirm C₂ physiology in this plant.

Table1- Plant species selected for Leaf anatomy repository

Species	Family	Local Name	Type
Monocot			
<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i> (L.) R. Br	Poaceae	Bajra	C ₄
<i>Chloris virgata</i> Sw.	Poaceae	jaranio	C ₄
<i>Brachairia reptans</i> (L.) C.A. Gardner & C.E. Hubb.	Poaceae	Murat	C ₄
<i>Brachairia remosa</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	Murat	C ₄
<i>Lasiurus scindicus</i> Henrard	Poaceae	Sewan	C ₄
<i>Panicum turgidum</i> Forssk	Poaceae	Switch grass	C ₄
<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Poaceae	Marvel grass	C ₄
<i>Cenchrus setigerus</i> Vahl	Poaceae	Bhurut	C ₄
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	Poaceae	Rice; Chawal	C ₃
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.	Poaceae	Wheat, Genhu	C ₃
<i>Cyperus rotendus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	Java grass	C ₄
Dicots			
<i>Mollugo cerviana</i> (L.) Ser.	Molluginaceae	Chiria-ro-khet	C ₄
<i>M. nudicaulis</i> Lam.	Molluginaceae	Naked Stem Carpetweed; Paprastaka	C ₃ -C ₄
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L	Asteraceae	Santa-Maria, Gajar Ghans	C ₃ -C ₄
<i>Farsetia hamiltonii</i> Royle	Brassicaceae	Hiran Chabo	C ₃ -C ₄
<i>Gisekia pharnaceoides</i> Linn.	Gisekiaceae		C ₄
<i>Corbichonia decumbens</i> (Forssk.) Exell	Lophiocarpaceae	Carpet-Weed	C ₃
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.	Zygophyllaceae	Chhota Gokhru	C ₄
<i>T. rajasthensis</i> Bhandari & V.S.Sharma	Zygophyllaceae	Chhota Gokhru, Kanti	C ₄
<i>Dipetrygium glaucum</i> Decne.	Cleomaceae	Safrawi	C ₃
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumach. & Thonn	Phyllantheaceae	Stone breaker, Gugario	C ₃
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Portulacaceae	Purskane, chicken weed	CAM
<i>P. umbraticola</i> L.	Portulacaceae	Purskane, chicken weed	CAM
<i>P. grandiflora</i> Hook.	Portulacaceae	Moss rose purslane	C ₄ -CAM
<i>Heliotropium zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) Lam.	Boraginaceae	Kali Bui	C ₄
<i>H. bacciferum</i> Forssk.	Boraginaceae	Kali Bui	C ₄
<i>H. marifolium</i> Koen. Ex Retz.	Boraginaceae	Chhoti- Santari	C ₄
<i>H. curassavicum</i> L.	Boraginaceae	Salt heliotrope	C ₃

Fig 1: - Monocot species with leaf anatomy. Crop plants *Triticum aestivum* and *Oryza sativa* are C₃ crops plants taken as comparison with desert grown natural grasses. The anatomy evidenced here the cell thickness, bundle sheath area and bulliform cells. C₄ grasses clearly show the presence of Kranz of mesophyll cells. Scale bar= 1 mm

Species	Morphology	Leaf Anatomy
<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i> (L.) Stapf		
<i>Brachiaria reptans</i> (Linn.) Gardner & Hubbard		
<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf		
<i>Chloris virgata</i> Sw.		
<i>Lasiurus scindicus</i> Henrard Sewan grass		

<p><i>Panicum turgidum</i> Forssk.</p>			
<p><i>Pennisetum glaucum</i> (Linn.) R. Br.</p>			
<p><i>Cenchrus setigerus</i> Vahl</p>			
<p><i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.</p>			
<p><i>Oryza sativa</i> Linn.</p>			
<p><i>Cyperus rotendus</i> Linn.</p>			

Fig 2: Leaf anatomical features of Dicot species of C3, CAM, C4 and intermediate plants. Scale bar = 1 mm

Species	Morphology	Leaf Anatomy
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> Linn.		
<i>T. rajasthanensis</i> Bhandari et Sharma		
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.		
<i>Farsetia hamiltonii</i> Royle		
<i>Mollugo nudicaulis</i> Lam.		

<p><i>Heliotropium paniculatum</i> R. Br</p>		
<p><i>Heliotropium bacciferum</i> Forssk.</p>		
<p><i>Heliotropium marifolium</i> Koen. ex Retz</p>		
<p><i>Heliotropium zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) Lam.</p>		
<p><i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i> Linn.</p>		
<p><i>Dipterygium glaucum</i> Decne.</p>		

Fig. 3: Leaf anatomy of *Farsetia hamiltonii*: Typical anatomical characteristics, indicating C_3 features, include both types of mesophyll cells (PMC, Palisade Mesophyll Cells, and SMC, Spongy Mesophyll Cells) containing chloroplasts. Furthermore, the leaf sections exhibit two types of chloroplasts within the bundle sheath-centripetal and centrifugal-reminiscent of a C_3 - C_4 intermediate plant. Scale bar = 5 mm. All images are copyrighted to authors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors acknowledges the Department of Botany, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur for providing research facilities.

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